

Deliverable 1.7

‘Programme of events to build collaboration between project partners and key stakeholders’

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Executive summary

The EUTOPIA Alliance is a collaboration between ten universities in Belgium, France, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, the UK, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Romania. One of the EU-funded projects under the EUTOPIA umbrella is called TRAIN (Transformation of Research and Innovation). Supported by the Horizon 2020 'Science With and for Society' initiative, the goal of TRAIN is to pool the resources and expertise of the six founding partners in order to develop a common Research and Innovation strategy for the alliance.

The outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN will fall primarily into three categories:

- Mapping and evaluation reports
- New tools to facilitate collaboration
- New strategic documents or policy recommendations

Stakeholder engagement is crucial to the success of EUTOPIA-TRAIN; without input from key groups and individuals, its goals and outcomes will not be sustainable beyond the parameters of the project. This report collates and consolidates a broad range of activities across EUTOPIA-TRAIN work packages, categorized as either 'delivered' or 'upcoming'.

The report draws some key conclusions:

1. EUTOPIA-TRAIN has planned and implemented over 40 stakeholder activities during the first two years of the project.
2. Engagement and knowledge gathering activities have primarily targeted 'internal' stakeholders (i.e., staff, researchers and students).
3. Events have been planned and implemented through a grassroots bottom-up approach, rooted in individual work package and tasks, rather than through a programmatic methodology.

The report will be used by the alliance to:

1. Reflect on the value of these initiatives (content/evaluations by participants and reach/target participants).
2. Select, plan and announce future events more in advance (where possible).
3. Identify potential thematic gaps that are key for the alliance.

Institutional Abbreviations

CY Cergy Paris Université	CYU
Göteborgs Universitet	GU
Univerza v Ljubljani	UL
Universitat Pompeu Fabra	UPF
University of Warwick	UoW
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB

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1. Introduction

This document and the accompanying ‘functional calendars’ constitute the EUTOPIA-TRAIN deliverable 1.7, described in TRAIN bid as a ‘programme of events to build collaboration between project partners and key stakeholders’ (p.12).

1.1. Acknowledgements

In addition to the authors credited on the title pages, we wish to acknowledge our other colleagues in TRAIN WP1: Sigridur Beck & Andreea Maris (Göteborgs Universitet) Simona Rataj (Univerza v Ljubljani), Tania Van Loon (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Frédéric Vidal & Armando Uribe-Echeverria (CY Cergy Paris Université) and Eva Martin Garcia (Universitat Pompeu Fabra). They have all contributed by engaging in discussions about the format and scope of the deliverable and giving feedback on the initial draft. In addition, we would also like to thank Wendy Coy (University of Warwick), Elisa Maes, Lennart Stoy & Floor Keersmaekers (Vrije Universiteit Brussel) and Sylvie Niessen (CY Cergy Paris Université). These colleagues have provided essential information about stakeholder activities within their individual TRAIN WPs.

1.2. Objectives of the deliverable

As outlined in the bid, under Task 1.5 Dissemination and Stakeholder Involvement Programme (p.11):

EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners will **work with stakeholders to establish the questions for consideration; the second stage will involve the mutual production of knowledge about that agreed area or issue; and the final stage will produce insights and policy/ practice recommendations.** This methodology will make use of a number of different formats. In the earlier stages of the project, there will be more of a reliance on virtual events and meetings between EUTOPIA-TRAIN partners and key stakeholders. As the project progresses, and especially when insights and recommendations about policy are being developed, a range of events and meetings (both physical and virtual) will provide policy makers, opinion-formers, higher education specialists and other sector specialists with access to project outcomes and opportunities to debate them. Possible formats for these events will include private policy roundtables, personal briefings, and open workshops. Events will be either WP-specific or address cross-cutting issues, the exact theme for each engagement will be identified as the project progresses, decided in conjunction with the Work Package (WP) leads. Events, organised by different EUTOPIA partners, will take place in locations most relevant to each chosen theme or WP, including policy-focused events in Brussels.

Stakeholder engagement is crucial to the success of EUTOPIA-TRAIN. Without input from key stakeholders, the project goals and outcomes will not be sustainable in the long term. The function of WP1 and the purpose of D1.7 is to collate and consolidate existing stakeholder events across TRAIN and measure progress against the key indicators set out in [D1.6 \(Plan for engagement and dissemination\)](#) Through this process, WP1 will evaluate existing activities, identify potential gaps and offer recommendations to ensure stakeholder involvement in all aspects as the project moves forward in its final year. The events included in this report constitute a wide range of different formats including (but not limited to) meetings, workshops/webinars, training events, conferences

and networking events. Events will be categorized as either ‘delivered’ or ‘upcoming’ depending on the status at the point of submission of this deliverable. It is important to assert that not all activities outlined in this programme will be implemented due to limited resources and timeframe. Flexibility with adding and updating the programme is highly important as the project develops. Whilst it is anticipated that most activities will take place others may become recommendations for future implementation as part of EUTOPIA-MORE.

1.3. Definition of stakeholders

‘Stakeholder’ can be perceived as a ‘catch-all’ term which is difficult to define, particularly in relation to a large-scale project like EUTOPIA-TRAIN. For the purposes of this report, stakeholder will refer to one of the groups outlined below. As an initial stakeholder mapping exercise, WP1 asked all WPs for their key stakeholders which feed into a joint [stakeholder register](#). Although not exhaustive, the list below consolidates stakeholders from across individual WPs which, as anticipated, are largely overlapping and range from ‘external’ stakeholders such as National and Regional governments to ‘internal’ EUTOPIA staff, researchers, and students. It is important to note that the key stakeholder groups targeted in this deliverable, for knowledge gathering purposes, are primarily ‘internal’. External stakeholders will be targeted through the creation of specific outputs aimed at dissemination which will be addressed in the upcoming deliverable 1.8 (Programme of events and meetings to promote findings and produce recommendations) due in December 2023.

Key stakeholders
European Commission
National governments
Regional governments
FOR-EU network
European university alliances (EUA)
European universities
EU Open Science policy community
EUTOPIA strategic board
EUTOPIA advisory board
EUTOPIA executive board
EUTOPIA research community (MSCA Science and Innovation SIF Fellows, Young Leaders Academy YLA fellows etc.)
EUTOPIA student community (undergraduate & postgraduate)
EUTOPIA professional services (e.g. tech transfer offices, research & innovation/grant services, HR departments, Library staff (data stewards))
Internal university management/leadership/operations
Businesses and industry (local/international)
Investors and venture capitalists (local/international)
Science Business
The Guild and other European higher education networks (e.g. UNICA)
Enterprise Europe Network
University Industry Innovation network (UIIN)
European Institute of innovation and technology and the KICs

Other innovation/acceleration programmes
Expert community on research assessment
Education policy experts
EUTOPIA global partners

2. Stakeholder engagement events

This section of the report will identify how TRAIN work packages have collaborated with key stakeholders for knowledge gathering purposes. The list below is structured chronologically, where applicable, by work package (1-5).

2.1. WP1: Developing a Common Research & Innovation Agenda

2.1.1. FOR-EU meetings (delivered)

Representatives from WP1 attend 3-4 FOR-EU Research & Innovation subgroup meetings per year to exchange ideas and best practice.

2.1.2. Meetings with other EUAs (delivered)

EUTOPIA held a meeting with fellow European University Alliance, CIVIS, during EUTOPIA week in Brussels (June 2022) to exchange ideas and share best practice. During this EUTOPIA week, a joint [EUTOPIA x CIVIS conference](#) on “The Future of Higher Education in Europe” was organised at Université Libre de Bruxelles (partner of Vrije Universiteit Brussel). Plans to implement a joint conference with additional EUAs in 2023 are currently being formulated (see conclusion).

2.1.3. Meetings with vice rectors research (delivered & upcoming)

The vice rectors responsible for R&I policies at their universities gather regularly (in person and online) in order to exchange about their current policies and to discuss the future joint R&I agenda. They meet staff members who present specific deliverables/tasks (e.g. research infrastructure task force, upcoming Horizon Europe funding opportunities, the role of GLENN, Reform of Research Assessment).

2.2. WP2: Innovation for the 21st Century

In consultation with researchers, PhD students and business, WP2 is primarily tasked with identifying barriers and facilitators to successful engagement with innovative activity across EUTOPIA partner institutions. WP2 needs to work directly with these key stakeholders to gain a better understanding of their needs, to identify examples of good practice and barriers to engagement. The events outlined below have been conceived and developed from initial consultations carried out by WP2 members with researchers (62), PhD students (57) and external partners (81) but also draws on recommendations from reports produced by other TRAIN WPs including D5.1 (Report on the future role of GLENN office) which highlights that entrepreneurship support and awareness should be improved by fostering new activities and training among both researchers and students. Training surveys conducted by WP4 also indicate the need for additional support on entrepreneurship and

innovation awareness. This programme of activities will help to build two-way collaboration between project partners and key stakeholders around the topic of Innovation.

2.2.1. EUTOPIA-SIF Innovation training (delivered)

In conjunction with WP4, WP2 delivered in-person training for SIFs in Paris on 21 October 2022. Feedback was gathered from participants before and after the training session to assess effectiveness and impact. This feedback will inform subsequent EUTOPIA training offerings for SIF fellows.

2.2.2. EUTOPIA ‘Introduction to Innovation’ workshop (delivered)

73% of PhD students consulted by WP2 are interested in ‘innovation’ however 84% have not undertaken any training related to innovation or entrepreneurship during their PhD. This is due to multiple reasons including access, availability, time and interest. A two-hour online workshop led by Professor Andy Pardoe on 16 November 2022 was piloted by WP2 to raise awareness of ‘innovation’ amongst PhD students from all disciplines across the EUTOPIA alliance. Participants were asked to consider what innovation means, why it is important and how it could relate to their own research and impact. Participants were asked to complete some assessment questions before and after the workshop to gather feedback to inform EUTOPIA’s innovation strategy moving forward.

2.2.3. UNI.MINDS festival, connecting academia and industry (delivered)

The biggest Slovenian online festival for building innovation community and long-term partnerships between academia and international business.

We opened UNI.MINDS 2022 in a motivational style: we have heard why university-business collaboration is so important, then had a valuable insight into different funding opportunities in the field of “deep-tech” innovation. The first day of the festival concluded with Novartis in Slovenia: Researchers’ Day.

On the 2nd and 3rd day, the topics were divided into Food, Health, Climate, Manufacturing, Raw Materials and Urban Mobility. Internationally renowned experts presented global trends in their respective fields, followed by panel discussions and fireside chats between experts from business, academia, and decision-makers.

The full programme provided insight into the technologies and expertise of researchers from the University of Ljubljana, the University of Maribor, and the University of Primorska. Good practice examples of cooperation with local representatives of the EIT network and reflect on better systemic support for innovations were presented. Those who were thinking about a spin-out company, were able to get in touch with organisations that could help them.

2.2.4. EUTOPIA meets business (delivered)

EUTOPIA tested a joint visit to COSYLAB JSC in Ljubljana during EUTOPIA week. COSYLAB is the leading provider of software solutions for the world’s most complex, precise, and advanced systems, such

as particle accelerators, large telescope arrays, fusion reactors, innovative medical devices, and cancer therapy systems. WP2 members and other innovation related staff exchanged ideas with COSYLAB about future cooperation opportunities in the field of advanced cancer treatment and clean energy. COSYLAB's presentation, including the focus calls, has been disseminated to researchers across partner institutions. Expressions of interest from researchers will be submitted to COSYLAB. Plans for more EUTOPIA level meetings with business are currently underway for 2023.

2.2.5.EUTOPIA 'Innovation in Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities research' workshop (delivered)

60% of students interviewed have not engaged with business or industry and 87% students have not accessed innovation support structures, predominantly because they have not had an idea that they wanted to pursue. PhD students in arts and social science subjects were particularly unsure how their research connected with entrepreneurship and felt that innovation training tends to be aimed at STEM subjects. Currently there is a lack of targeted training geared towards arts and social science students across the EUTOPIA partners. Dr Bridget Sealey delivered a half-day online workshop on the fundamentals of innovation in the social sciences, arts and humanities research, offering pointers to resources and examples of best practice to help further development and learning. The workshop was open to all PhD students and Early Career Researchers from relevant disciplines across the alliance. This workshop, together with pre and post-workshop assessment questions, will help to inform EUTOPIA's understanding of needs and capacity within this community.

2.2.6.EUTOPIA 'Innovative PhDs' workshop (delivered)

Over half of PhD students consulted are not aware of opportunities to learn about innovation and entrepreneurship at their institutions. Training undertaken tends to be focused on research development. Students interviewed are unsure how innovation fits into their future goals and haven't considered the possibility of pursuing both simultaneously. An 'Innovative PhDs' workshop was implemented on 14 December 2022 to facilitate discussion amongst Innovation support staff and researchers, who are current or future supervisors, around the empowerment of PhD students to explore entrepreneurship as a career alongside their degree.

2.2.7. 'Innovation rewards and incentives' focus group meeting (upcoming)

Only 22% of PhD students interviewed said that there are clear incentives and reward structures for engaging in innovative activity at their institution, but most students said that a reward structure would, or might, motivate them further. Students appear to be primarily incentivized by mobility opportunities and outputs for their research rather than financial gain with several referring to departmental or institutional level award schemes as positive motivators. This focus group meeting will ask both students and researchers to explore ideas for reward structure pilot models.

2.2.8. 'How to collaborate with industrial partners' workshop (upcoming)

This interactive workshop will gauge current level of understanding amongst researchers and PhD students about industrial partnerships. Led by WP2 members from University of Ljubljana, this

workshop will equip stakeholders with a better understanding of the industrial mindset and development process, where to find industrial partners for cooperation and how to start conversations with companies. Participants will be asked to complete pre and post workshop questions to gather feedback and to assess the impact of the session.

2.2.9. 'How should universities engage with business' focus group meeting (upcoming)

This focus group meeting will provide more in-depth consultation with a select number of external stakeholders about how universities should engage with them.

2.2.10. Sustainability Training School (upcoming)

Warwick's Institute for Global Sustainable Development, in collaboration with EUTOPIA and other strategic partner-HEIs, sets to launch and develop regular Sustainability Training Schools (STS) for Early Career Researchers (ECRs - PhDs and Postdocs) and Young Leaders (YLA) focusing on sustainable development goals and their innovative solutions. The overall objective is to nurture a new generation of responsible and caring researchers and citizens with responsibility for the planetary well-being.

2.2.11. University Industry Innovation Network (UIIN) 2023 Conference (upcoming)

WP2 plan to disseminate findings and engage with a wider international audience of stakeholders at through a specific EUA track at the UIIN conference (9-11 May 2023).

2.3. WP3: Open Science and Societal Outreach

Sharing resources in Open Access is a way for EUTOPIA to lead by example in the implementation of Open Science. By making knowledge, experience and good practices openly available, this practice can strengthen EUTOPIA's high-level policy impact as well as its impact on other universities and European University Alliances in general. Open access to project outputs is a commitment enshrined in the EUTOPIA TRAIN Consortium Agreement (Art. 8.5.2). Of course, making resources available is not enough to reach different audiences – more specific actions and channels for dissemination and engagement are listed below.

2.3.1. EUTOPIA Week Open Science session (UPF 2021) (delivered)

WP3 organised a session on EUTOPIA Open Science activities in EUTOPIA2050 and EUTOPIA-TRAIN in November 2021 with a presentation from the European University Association (EUA) on latest Open Science survey results. This event aimed to increase awareness of EUTOPIA community around Open Science in ongoing projects; collect ideas and suggestions from EUA survey on Open Science for future actions.

2.3.2. *Open Science Webinar (delivered)*

Introductory webinar on Open Science ('Why and how') took place on 25 October 2021 including external experts involved with CoData and FAIRsFAIR (WP3.1). This event aimed to increase awareness and motivate Open Science activities of EUTOPIA researchers.

2.3.3. *Open Science in Horizon Europe Webinar (delivered)*

Webinar with expert speakers on Open Science requirements and practices in Horizon Europe; external presenters from European Commission (Open Science Unit) and Open Research Europe (WP3.1). This event provided information on Open Science in Horizon Europe for researchers, Open Science experts and other EUTOPIA staff.

2.3.4. *Workshop on research assessment (delivered)*

EUTOPIA-wide online workshop on assessment to start work in WP3.3. Featured presentation from EUA expert on Research assessment (Vice president from Open University of Catalunya) (WP3.3). This event provided examples of institutional good practice to the EUTOPIA community; discussed basic principles for Open Science in assessment with the EUTOPIA community.

2.3.5. *Citizen Science webinars (delivered)*

Two Citizen Science webinars organised with UNICA Network (WP3.4) delivered in February and May 2022 to train the EUTOPIA community on Citizen Science issues; build an external network on Citizen Sciences and collect feedback from them.

2.3.6. *EUTOPIA workshop on Open Science strategy (delivered)*

Workshop with EUTOPIA community during VUB EUTOPIA Week 2022 in June 2022 (WP3). This event aimed to increase awareness of EUTOPIA community around Open Science in ongoing project; collect ideas and suggestions for Open Science in Research & Innovation Strategy.

2.3.7. *Citizen Science clinics (delivered & upcoming)*

EUTOPIA-TRAIN Citizen Science clinics are informal sessions with researchers and citizen science experts to discuss current issues and challenges in their research. The creation of a Citizen Science Community of Practice enables the exchange of expertise and experience across Citizen Science stakeholders in EUTOPIA. Clinics around specific themes have already taken place on 8 March 2022, 26 April 2022, 7 June 2022, 13 October 2022, 17 November 2022 and 15 December 2022. These events are reoccurring with more sessions planned for 2023.

2.3.8. *Presentation at the Networking Day of Scivil (delivered)*

Presentation at the Networking Day of [Scivil](#), Flanders' Knowledge Center on Citizen Science on 15 November 2022 to increase awareness of EUTOPIA Citizen Science activities and usage of resources

(e.g. training kit) amongst other universities and research institutions, local governments and Citizen Science researchers and experts.

2.3.9. Poster at Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing (delivered)

Poster at Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing on 30 November 2022 to raise awareness of EUTOPIA Open Science activities amongst other universities and Open Sciences experts.

2.3.10. Presentation at EOSCfuture event “Pan-European digital assets supporting research communities – Benefits & opportunities” (delivered)

Presentation of EUTOPIA and the EUTOPIA Open Research Portal in particular (WP3.2) at EOSCfuture event on 5 December 2022. Dissemination of EUTOPIA Open Research Portal and EUTOPIA Open Science activities towards external audience, collection of feedback and ideas from other communities.

2.3.11. Webinar on Reproducible Research (delivered)

EUTOPIA session on reproducibility and replicability on 9 December during VUB Ethics Week 2022; participation of experts affiliated with Portuguese Reproducibility Network and ReproducibiliTea (WP3.1). This event aimed to increase awareness of reproducibility practices and issues across VUB and EUTOPIA researchers; highlight existing networks and initiatives on reproducibility and engage with them.

2.3.12. Institutional workshops on Open Science in research assessment (upcoming)

Institutional consultation workshops on research assessment framework to collect institutional level feedback on EUTOPIA research assessment framework. VUB delivered an institutional workshop in October 2022, other partners still to implement.

2.3.1. Presentation at EARMA 2023 Annual Conference (upcoming)

Presentation at the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators EARMA 2023 conference in April 2023 to increase awareness of EUTOPIA Citizen Science activities and recourses amongst other universities and Citizen Sciences experts (WP3.4). The abstract has been selected for a Pecha Kucha session.

2.4. WP4: Human Capital

The key stakeholders for WP4 are researchers, specifically the Young Leaders Academy (YLA) and Science & Innovation Fellows (SIFs), along with HR professionals across the EUTOPIA alliance. Stakeholder engagement activities, relating to training, have been primarily required input from other TRAIN WPs (see 2.2.1, 2.5.5, 2.5.6 & 2.5.7).

2.4.1. HR Directors Meetings (delivered)

The HR Directors Group meets regularly and comprises representatives from each of the six respective HR departments and is chaired by the HR director at VUB. The results of the Working Group will feed into the EUTOPIA HR Roadmap.

2.4.2. YLA Symposium on “Impact in Research: a European Perspective” (delivered)

During the EUTOPIA week in Brussels (30 June 2022), the VUB YLA’s organised a symposium aiming to reflect on different meanings and types of impact, ways of measuring impact, and the potential role of EUTOPIA in fostering impact in research. In person and online, open participation, with external (European Commission, European Research Council and the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)) as well as EUTOPIA speakers.

2.4.3. YLA Impact training session (upcoming)

In conjunction with the University of Warwick, WP4 will deliver online sessions on ‘Introduction to Impact’ and ‘Measurement & Evaluation of Impact’ for the YLAs on 24 March 2023.

2.5. WP5: Grants, Legal and Innovation Office (GLENN)

The GLENN office stakeholders are primarily researchers and research and innovation support staff across the alliance.

2.5.1. GLENN Research Information Systems session (delivered)

Online session for members of the GLENN office and institutional data & information teams who develop/maintain similar databases to get inspired by other systems and consider possible improvements if needed. This Feb. 2022 event created an opportunity to exchange knowledge between stakeholders on the main features and search functions of our existing databases and gather input for potential improvements to current systems. It also led to the creation of a [EUTOPIA webpage](#) listing all existing central research information systems accessible to external users. This allows the EUTOPIA research community to look for / contact research groups and researchers from the 10 partners.

2.5.2. EUTOPIA gender week webinar (delivered)

An open online session was jointly organised in March 2022 by CYU and VUB. It aimed at raising awareness of researchers from the EUTOPIA partners and beyond on institutional initiatives from their gender action plans, and on the value of gendered research & innovation for knowledge-building.

2.5.3. UPF International Staff Training Days (ISTD) (delivered)

The ISTDs, hosted by UPF, took place over 9-11 May 2022 framed around the topics of Internationalization at home and Research & Innovation. Participants were primarily administrative staff from EUTOPIA partners and other international HEIs working in the fields of international education, research and innovation.

2.5.4. GLENN Staff week (delivered)

Following on from the ISTDs, WP5 organised a series of GLENN focus group meetings over 12-13 May 2022 on the topics of Pre-award support services in ERC grants, Innovation services and Gender issues in Horizon Europe. A range of stakeholders including GLENN officers and other relevant staff, with specialist knowledge, from partner institution attended these meetings.

2.5.5. YLA meet GLENN workshop (delivered)

A 'YLA meet GLENN' workshop was held in person in Brussels during EUTOPIA week (June 2022). The main purpose of the workshop was to get YLA's input on concrete services EUTOPIA can provide in order to support them in initiating new collaborations. Outcomes of these discussions were fed back to the GLENN office.

2.5.6. GLENN meet your peers workshop (delivered)

A 'GLENN meet your peers' workshop was held in person in Brussels during EUTOPIA week (June 2022). The workshop gave the opportunity to EUTOPIA grant offices staff from to present their services in supporting research proposals development and post-award support, and to highlight some EUTOPIA research services and outcomes achieved by GLENN so far. It was the first in person meeting of grant office representatives from the 10 partners.

2.5.7. EUTOPIA-SIF training on Research funding and career/ post doc opportunities (delivered)

In conjunction with WP4, WP5 delivered a training session for the EUTOPIA-SIF Fellows on 15 December 2022 around research funding and career/postdoctoral opportunities focussing on National/Regional programmes open to EUTOPIA researchers.

2.5.8. Yellow Research ERC training sessions (upcoming)

Building on input from the Pre-Award focus group discussion during the GLENN staff week, WP5 is organising a European Research Council (ERC) Starting Grants (StG) and Consolidator Grants (CoG) training session delivered by the research training consultancy company, Yellow Research. Each partner will be allocated 9/10 places. The sessions will take place online on Tuesday 28 March 2023 and Thursday 30 March 2023.

2.5.9. EUTOPIA MSCA-Postdoctoral Fellowship Info Day (upcoming)

WP5 will organise an info day for EUTOPIA researchers to highlight the forthcoming MSCA-Postdoctoral Fellowship 2023 call and how to use the EUTOPIA MSCA partnering tool.

2.5.10. EUTOPIA Networking events (upcoming)

WP5 will organise a series of online networking events in 2023 for targeted research groups (e.g. Connected Research Communities and EUTOPIA-SIFs) who are interested in creating consortia and applying for EU funding calls (e.g. Missions, Widening calls).

2.6. EUTOPIA weeks

Bi-annual 'EUTOPIA weeks' have become an important way for the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project to connect with stakeholders across EUTOPIA (2050, MORE etc.). Since January 2021, EUTOPIA-TRAIN has had been involved in EUTOPIA weeks taking place in Gothenburg (online), Barcelona (in person), Brussels (in person) and Ljubljana (in person). Looking ahead, EUTOPIA-TRAIN will also feature heavily in forthcoming EUTOPIA weeks taking place in Lisbon (June 2023) and Dresden (December 2023).

3. Functional calendar

3.1. Public calendar

CY Cergy has developed a dedicated [TRAIN news](#) webpage on the new TRAIN website which maps stakeholder activities and events chronologically. This calendar of events is public and available to wider audiences.

3.2. Functional calendar

The University of Warwick has developed a ‘functional’ or ‘working’ calendar on the [EUTOPIA-TRAIN SharePoint](#) as way of tracking stakeholder engagement activity across the project. This calendar can be used by WPs to record events but also document meetings and pilots that are not open to wider audiences. This calendar will enable colleagues to plan and implement activities in conjunction with other WPs, highlighting potential overlap and reducing risk of duplication. Ultimately, this will help to facilitate a more coherent approach to stakeholder engagement.

4. Conclusions and future working

The programme of events indicates that EUTOPIA-TRAIN is engaging with ‘internal’ stakeholders identified in the [stakeholder register](#) and meeting key indicators for engagement outlined in [D1.6 \(Plan for engagement and dissemination\)](#). Quantitative data for stakeholder engagement is difficult to obtain due to overlap between different activities and audiences. Similarly, some events are standalone while others are reoccurring. More than 40 stakeholder activities have been included in this report falling into roughly five different categories: meetings, workshops/webinars, training events, conferences, and networking events:

Meetings: 7

Workshops/webinars: 18

Training events: 7

Conferences: 5

Networking events: 4

It is important to note that in addition to the activities outlined in this report, TRAIN stakeholders are regularly engaged and consulted through a series of internal meetings including the TRAIN Management Board meetings (strategic) and TRAIN WP leads meetings (operational). Furthermore, individual WP meetings and task force meetings ensure that relevant colleagues, with specialist knowledge, across partners institutions are engaged in the development of the project. YLA Steering Committee meetings and EUTOPIA-SIF Programme management meetings also take place on a regular basis to ensure full stakeholder engagement.

Stakeholder engagement events have been conceived and implemented at a grassroots level through a range of different activities which will ultimately help to shape and develop EUTOPIA-TRAIN’s outputs. Stakeholder engagement and event planning has been ‘bottom-up’, rooted in individual work packages and tasks, rather than ‘programmatic’. As the project progresses, TRAIN WP1 will begin to weave a more unified and coherent programme into this bottom-up approach to avoid oversaturation, maximize participation and streamline workload across work packages and partners. EUTOPIA’s new partners and global partners will continue to be included and consulted as much as possible to ensure wide reach for ongoing stakeholder engagement. EUTOPIA-TRAIN colleagues should also liaise with counterparts working on EUTOPIA-MORE to facilitate a joined-up approach to stakeholder engagement.

This report will be used by the alliance to:

1. Reflect on the value of these initiatives (content/evaluations by participants and reach/target participants).
2. Select, plan and announce future events more in advance (where possible).
3. Identify potential thematic gaps that are key for the alliance.

Looking ahead to the final year of EUTOPIA-TRAIN, WP1 will oversee the delivery of D1.8 (Programme of events and meetings to promote findings and produce recommendations) which is due in December 2023. This deliverable will comprise a variety of dissemination activities from

individual work packages aimed at EUTOPIA's 'external' stakeholders including (but not limited to) other EUAs, policy makers and regional and national governments. A large-scale joint event, in Brussels, bringing together other EUAs coming to the end of their SwafS projects, will be coordinated and implemented by WP1 at the end of 2023. This event will facilitate the sharing of best practice between EUAs on a large, international platform to maximize project impact.